

The phenomenon of professional burn-out of civil servants (the case study of the executive authorities of the Mykolaiv region)

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Abstract. The aim of the paper is to determine the phenomenon of professional burn-out of civil servants. The study involved civil servants of various ranks and positions from the regional justice bodies, the Pension Fund, Mykolaiv Regional State Administration and District State Administrations of the Mykolaiv region (Ukraine). The study was planned and carried out with the theoretical assumption that those people who have been working in the organization for more than three years may experience professional burnout. Therefore, the pilot research included people who have been working in an organization from three to twenty-five years. In total 300 people took part in the research: civil servants of executive authorities of the Mykolaiv region (171 females and 129 males) from 25 to 55 years of age. The research stage of the study included usage of inventories that allowed diagnosing the typical manifestations of burnout – anxiety and nervous tension, professional stress, decreased subjective quality of life and depersonalization. The obtained research results signify that civil servants of executive bodies express various manifestations of “professional burnout” syndrome. In particular, more than half of the respondents exhibit the symptoms of anxiety and nervous tension, 70% of the total number of respondents has high rates of mental burnout. Most respondents also have a medium level of emotional exhaustion and depersonalization, and high level of personal achievement.

1 Introduction

The socio-economic changes and political transformations that are currently taking place in Ukraine are the leading cause of increasing tensions and an challenging work atmosphere among government officials, as their work is directly linked to these changes.

At the same time, the professional activities of civil servants influence not only the formation of citizens' trust in state institutions, but it also creates the qualitatively new level of state responsibility to its citizens for the realization of their rights, freedoms and legitimate interests. Current state of affairs requires highly professional, creative and energetic people to be present and engaged at all levels of the state system. The system needs professional people who are able to lead complex transformational processes and direct changes in the priority areas of the capacity building of state institutions. Therefore, personal and professional development of civil servants and local government officials should be one of the main priorities in any democratic state. At the same time high demands which are placed on civil servants cause them to experience professional and emotional stress, physical and psychological exhaustion, nervous overload, and so on. The phenomenon of professional burnout of civil servants provokes academic and practical interest as it is a direct manifestation of the problems related to their professional activities, emotional, mental and physical condition, social and family environments.

It should be noted that scholars still do not have a general consensus concerning the psychological structure of burnout. At the theoretical level the understanding of the essence of burnout, its structure and stages is quite contradictory. This could be explained by the different approaches used for the analysis of burnout and its integral parts. Each of these approaches focuses only on a specific aspect of burnout and highlights only one group of factors and indicators.

However, burnout is widely covered in the works of many scholars. Today psychologists have been thoroughly considering this phenomenon in the context of “emotional burnout” of teachers, social workers, athletes, managers, medical workers, preschool educators and other categories of people. Also fairly recently the studies were launched on the manifestations of professional stress and burnout syndrome in military personnel and law enforcement officers. At the same time, the psychological characteristics of the professional activities of civil servants, which cause the burnout, remain underresearched. In particular, issues related to the psychological factors of professional burnout and ways to overcome or prevent it are practically unexplored. One of the primary reasons for this is connected with the previously closed nature of the profession of a civil servant.

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2 Theory and methods of research

2.1 The phenomenon of “professional burnout”: the essence and main approaches to its study

There is a multitude of factors that affect employees of private and state companies, including civil servants and government officials. The fast pace of life, new demands from the society on the qualifications and professional level of civil servants and government officials, socio-political and socio-economic changes taking place in Ukraine undoubtedly affect their psychological wellbeing, provoke emotional and professional stress as well as lead to professional deformation.

The scholars use the concept of “professional destruction” where professional destruction is a change in the structure of an activity and personality, which negatively affects productivity and interaction with other participants of this process.

Generalizing the research on the deviations connected with the professional development of a person it is possible to single out the following tendencies of professional destructions:

- low professional mobility, inability to adapt to new working conditions and maladaptation;
- inconsistency of certain stages of professional development, when one area is developing and the other is lagging behind (for example, a person has motivation for professional growth but at the same time lacks holistic professional consciousness);
- weakening of previously acquired professional abilities and professional thinking;
- distorted professional development, the emergence of negative qualities that did not exist before, deviations from social and individual norms of professional development;
- onset of personality deformations (e.g. emotional exhaustion, burnout, etc.);
- termination of professional development due to occupational diseases or disability.

The syndrome of “professional burnout” is still one of the understudied phenomena of personal deformation.

At the present professional burnout is studied by various branches of psychology: psychology of stressful states (burnout is regarded as a result of stress), within the workplace psychology (burnout is regarded as a form of professional deformation) and existential psychology (burnout is seen as a state of physical and mental exhaustion resulting from prolonged exposure to emotionally stressful situations). Professional burnout has been studied by international psychologists for more than thirty-five years.

Professional burnout is a reaction of a human body and psyche that occurs as a result of a prolonged exposure to medium-intensity stress caused by the professional activities and is the result of an uncontrolled long-term stress. At the same time, a mental state which is characterized by feelings of emotional devastation and fatigue caused by work, with combination of emotional devastation, depersonalization and reduction or complete leveling of professional achievements is a kind and prerequisite for professional deformation of a personality.

Most researchers believe that such concepts as “fatigue”, “stress”, “nervous exhaustion”, “professional deformation”, “burnout” are, although related, but relatively independent phenomena. Hence, there is a need to clearly delineate the concept of “professional burnout” from the above related concepts.

The key difference between “burnout” and “fatigue” is that in the latter case a person is able to quickly restore its own strength as opposed to burnout.

Differentiating the concepts of “professional deformation” and “professional burnout”, it should be noted that scholars consider professional deformation as a combination of personality aspects which have been formed during professional activities, and which have a negative connotation and are manifested mainly in non-professional life. Burnout is an entirely professional phenomenon which may not affect person's activities and wellbeing in the non-professional sphere of life. Deformation of personality traits is manifested at later stages of professional career, and burnout can occur at the beginning of professional life due to the mismatch between the requirements of the profession and the aspirations of the individual.

Thus, based on the analysis of the literature, one can conclude that burnout is a mental, emotional and physical exhaustion that develops due to long-term professional stress.

2.2. Psychodiagnostic tools for determining structural elements of professional burnout of civil servants

Table 1 presents the tools used to determine burnout and personality destructions that accompany it.

Table 1. Psychodiagnostic tools for determining structural elements of professional burnout of civil servants

Structural elements of professional burnout	Methods for determining the parameters of professional burnout
Anxiety and nervous tension	Spielberger's State-Trait Anxiety Inventory
Professional stress	Maslach's and Jackson's Burnout Inventory

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Values: value orientations and value representations	Inventory for measuring self-actualization of a person
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Spielberger's State-Trait Anxiety Inventory. This test is a reliable source of information about a person's self-assessment of the anxiety level at the moment (reactive anxiety) and personal anxiety (as a stable characteristic of the person). Personal anxiety characterizes a persistent tendency to perceive a wide range of situations as threatening, to respond to such situations with a state of anxiety. Reactive anxiety is characterized by tension, anxiety and nervousness. Very high reactive anxiety sometimes causes impairment of attention and fine motor coordination. Very high personal anxiety is directly correlated with the presence of a neurotic conflict, with emotional and neurotic breakdowns and psychosomatic illnesses.

However, at the early stages anxiety is not a negative trait. A certain level of anxiety is a natural and obligatory feature of an active personality. Also there is an optimal individual level of "useful anxiety".

Significant deviations from the moderate level of anxiety require special attention of qualified specialists. High levels of anxiety imply a tendency to exhibit anxiety in situations where a person evaluates its own competence. In this case, the subjective significance of the situation and tasks should be decreased. The emphasis should be shifted towards understanding the essence of the activities and forming a sense of confidence in success.

Low anxiety, on the other hand, requires increased attention to the motives of the activity and an increased sense of responsibility. However, sometimes very low anxiety levels on the test scores are the result of the active displacement of high anxiety by the individual in order to show oneself in a "better light".

Maslach's and Jackson's Burnout Inventory. The inventory is designed to measure the degree of burnout in professions which involve "human-human" interactions (but can be used for other types of professions). It is the main inventory for detecting professional burnout. Respondents determine how often they experience the feelings listed in the questionnaire according to a certain scale. The questionnaire has three scales:

- "emotional exhaustion" (manifested in the feelings of reduced emotional tone, loss of interest in the environment or emotional oversaturation; aggressive reactions, anger attacks, the onset of symptoms of depression);
- "depersonalization" (manifested in the deformation, or depersonalization of relationships with other people: increased dependence on others or, conversely, negativism, cynical attitudes and feelings about colleagues and clients);
- "decrease of personal achievements" (manifested in the tendency of having negative self-esteem, in diminishing the importance of one's own achievements, limiting one's capabilities, negativism towards job responsibilities, decreased professional motivation, exonerating oneself from responsibility or alienation from others).

Inventory for measuring self-actualization of a person. Abraham Maslow introduced the concept of self-actualization, which meant the highest human need manifested in the active desire to discover abilities, personal development and hidden potential in a person. Self-actualizing personality, according to his ideas, is endowed with many positive traits, such as impartiality, greater objectivity in the perception of reality, less emotionality (less prone to fears and hopes), resilience (less anxiety and ability to cope with problems and contradictions), independence and autonomy. Such person feels the joy of life and at the same time, strives for self-development, fully accepts oneself. The result of the research was the "Personal Orientation Inventory" (POI). The inventory consisted of two main scales of personal orientation: 1) "Time competence" scale, which shows how much a person is able to live in the present, without postponing it to the future and without trying to return to the past; 2) "Inner-directed" scale, which measures the ability of an individual to use one's own resources, rather than expect smth from others. In addition, there were ten additional scales that measured affirmation of primary values, spontaneity, capacity for intimate contact, acceptance of aggression, etc.

2.3 Research methodology

The psychological research on the professional burnout of civil servants and method of its prevention involved participants from the executive authorities of the Mykolaiv region (Ukraine)

The study took place in 2019 and included three stages. The first stage, organizational, encompassed clarification of the purpose and tasks of the research, selection of the diagnostic methods and instruments, creation of the research participant groups, analysis of theoretical background on the concept of professional burnout. Additionally, approaches and strategies for overcoming burnout of civil servants have been studied at this stage. The second stage, research, included the study of the burnout's impact on the professional activities of civil servants. The third stage, analytical, comprised the analysis, data comparison, creation and selection of the recommendations for the professional burnout prevention strategies.

The study involved civil servants of various ranks and positions from the regional justice bodies, the Pension Fund, Mykolaiv Regional State Administration and District State Administrations of the Mykolaiv region (Ukraine). The study was planned and carried out with the theoretical assumption that those people who have been working in the organization for more than three years may experience professional burnout. Therefore, the pilot research included people who have been working in an organization from three to twenty-five years. In total 300 people took part in the research: civil servants of executive authorities of the Mykolaiv region (171 females and 129 males) from 25 to 55 years

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of age. The research stage of the study included usage of inventories that allowed diagnosing the typical manifestations of burnout – anxiety and nervous tension, professional stress, decreased subjective quality of life and depersonalization.

3. Results

The analytical stage of the research included measuring professional burnout indicators of 300 civil servants who work at various executive authorities of the Mykolaiv region.

Table 2 presents results of a study of the level of anxiety and nervous tension on the Spielberg’s State-Trait Anxiety Inventory. Figure 1 shows the levels of anxiety listed in the table.

Table 2. Levels of anxiety and nervous tension

Indicators		Average score	Number of respondents (%)
Trait anxiety	Low	25	3,3
	Medium	33,2	80
	High	49,5	16,7
State anxiety	Low	26,5	16,7
	Medium	36,2	50
	High	51,9	33,3

The results in Table 2 show that more than half of the respondents are in a state of anxiety and nervous tension. A third of respondents exhibited high rates of situational anxiety, characterized by tension, anxiety, nervousness.

Fig. 1. Levels of anxiety

State anxiety (reactive anxiety) – (situational anxiety, anxiety as a state at a given time) is characterized by subjectively experienced emotions: tension, anxiety, nervousness. This condition occurs as an emotional response to a stressful situation and can vary in intensity and dynamism over time. Usually anxiety has a reason, that is, a person knows why he or she is worried. In such situations anxiety can play a positive role, as it contributes to the concentration of energy to achieve the desired goal, the mobilization of the reserves of the body and personality to overcome possible difficulties.

Trait anxiety (personal anxiety) is a persistent condition. It characterizes a person's tendency to perceive a wide range of situations as threatening and to respond to such situations with anxiety. Very high level of trait anxiety is directly related to the presence of neurotic conflict, emotional and nervous breakdowns, psychosomatic diseases. Personal anxiety is usually diagnosed in people who seek to feel their need, importance and desire for career growth, positive management evaluations and do not receive them, which increases anxiety and leads to professional stress.

It should be noted that a certain level of anxiety is a natural and obligatory feature of an active personality. Therefore, the authors of this study call the medium level of anxiety “useful anxiety”.

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At the same time, a low level of anxiety, on the contrary, requires attention (i.e. the motives for an activity and a heightened sense of responsibility). In rare cases, anxiety may hide a protective psychological mechanism of displacement of real anxiety or the purpose of the subject “to show oneself in the better light”.

The authors of the study also identified the features of the respondents’ mental burnout indicators.

Table 3 shows the results of testing using Rukavishnikov’s Inventory of Mental Burnout with a graphical representation of the relationships on Figure 2.

Table 3. Indicators of mental burnout according to Rukavishnikov’s Inventory of Mental Burnout

Indicators		Average score	Number of respondents (%)
Psycho-emotional exhaustion	Very low	5	3,3
	Low	15,4	26,7
	Medium	29,7	36,7
	High	44,8	23,3
	Very high	52,7	10
Personal alienation	Very low	–	–
	Low	20	6,7
	Medium	25,2	53,3
	High	35	10
	Very high	46,2	30
Professional motivation	Very low	–	–
	Low	–	–
	Medium	24	3,3
	High	27,7	10
	Very high	45,3	86,7
Index of mental burnout	Very low	–	–
	Low	–	–
	Medium	75,1	30
	High	103,8	23,3
	Very high	134,2	46,7

According to Table 3, twenty one person (70% of the total number of respondents) had high rates of mental burnout.

Fig. 2. The ratio of mental burnout indicators

The content-related characteristics of the scales are as follows:

High and extremely high rates of psycho-emotional exhaustion were exhibited in 33.3% of the respondents. Such persons may be depleted of emotional, physical and psychological resources. Exhaustion is manifested in chronic emotional and physical fatigue, indifference and coldness towards others, manifestations of depression and irritability.

High and extremely high indicators on the scale “Personal alienation” were found in 40% of the respondents. The scale captures a specific form of social maladaptation of a professional. Personal alienation is manifested in a decreased number of contacts with others, increased irritability and intolerance in communication situations, negativism towards other people.

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High and extremely high indicators on the scale "Professional Motivation" were found in 96.7% of the respondents. Professional motivation is assessed by such indicators as professional productivity, optimism and interest in work-related activities, self-assessment of professional competence and the degree of success in working with people.

Almost 100% of civil servants have shown a high level of professional motivation, which is characterized by enthusiasm and interest in work, even at the expense of family life and self-interests that are not related to work. On the other hand, such people have a painful attitude to failures. They are constantly evaluating their own professional competence. Too high levels of professional motivation lead to rapid depletion, imbalance of life resources and ultimately accelerate emotional burnout.

At the same time, the index of mental burnout reflects the aggregate indicator on three scales and shows that there are no civil servants who would not have at least some of the manifestations of emotional burnout. On the contrary, high index of mental burnout is observed in 70% of the respondents.

Further research was aimed at studying the non-specific manifestations of professional burnout, namely: indicators of the respondents self-actualization.

Many scholars point out the connection between burnout and disruption of the self-actualization processes.

Table 4 shows the results obtained from the inventory "Diagnostics of self-actualization of personality".

Table 4. Research protocol of the level of desire for self-actualization

Scales	The level of desire for self-actualization (%)				
	Very low	Low	Medium	High	Very high
Time orientation	10	16,7	50	20	3,3
Values	0	40	40	20	0
View of the human nature	0	20	46,7	33,3	0
The need for knowledge	3,3	26,7	46,7	23,3	0
Creativity	0	33,3	66,7	0	0
Autonomy	0	33,3	60	6,7	0
Spontaneity	0	33,3	66,7	0	0
Understanding of self	0	30	53,3	10	6,7
Autosympathy	10	40	26,7	23,3	0
Rapport	0	0	66,7	33,3	0
Flexibility in communication	6,7	23,3	36,7	33,3	0
Total score	0	23,3	76,7	0	0

Analysis of the data from Table 4 shows that in general the obtained data are in the limits of average values. This means that a significant number of respondents has a certain meaning of life, and this is what their lives are aimed at. They are quite sthenic, viable, energetic in professional and everyday life. Thus, they can be described as self-actualized.

However, it should be noted that almost a third of respondents has a low level of self-actualization on eight scales, namely: "Values", "Need for Knowledge", "Creativity", "Autonomy", "Spontaneity", "Understanding of Self", "Autosympathy".

Low scores on the "Values" scale indicate that self-actualized respondents may not share all the values proposed by A. Maslow, because they were developed at another time and in another culture. However, this does not mean that the subjects do not have their own value system, as it may not completely coincide with the value system proposed by A. Maslow. At the same time, low scores on this scale may indicate a lack of desire for a harmonious life and healthy relationships with people, a tendency to manipulate others, lack of life prospects.

High scores on the "Need for knowledge" scale are a characteristic of a self-actualized personality, which is always open to new experiences. This scale describes an ability to know life – a selfless thirst for something new, an interest in objects that are not related to the satisfaction of any needs. Such knowledge is considered by A. Maslow to be more accurate and effective, because its process is not distorted by desires and inclinations.

Low levels of creativity indicate weak creative potential. Such people are characterized by stereotypical thinking, traditional problem solving methods and inability to generate new ideas. They are afraid to be different from others, show their own spontaneity and atypicality. That is, based on the above, it can be argued that low scores on the scale "Creativity" and "Need for Knowledge" are characteristic of people with a conservative mindset.

Analysis of low scores on the scales "Spontaneity", "Autosympathy" and "Autonomy" reveals obstacles that prevent the achievement of a high level of self-actualization. According to the representatives of humanistic psychology, autonomy is a criterion of the individual's integrity, one's maturity and self-sufficiency, and in combination with a positive self-assessment - also the basis of psychological health. Civil servants have become dependent on social stereotypes and standards. They are held hostages to their own social role, because, even with significant personal resources, they can not fully utilize them, but also feel dependent on the state due to its inconsistent policies.

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Thus, according to the obtained results, it can be stated that a third of the respondents has violated the mechanisms of self-determination and self-actualization. Accordingly, respondents cannot form final and intermediate goals and choose adequate means to achieve the goal as well as not able to evaluate the final and intermediate results. Moreover, their system of external and internal behavior control is distorted and they do not control their own life situations.

4 Conclusions

The obtained research results signify that civil servants of executive bodies of the Mykolaiv region express various manifestations of “professional burnout” syndrome. In particular, more than half of the respondents exhibit the symptoms of anxiety and nervous tension, more than two hundred respondent has high rates of mental burnout (70% of the total number of respondents). Most respondents also have a medium level of emotional exhaustion and depersonalization, and high level of personal achievement. The study also examined non-specific manifestations of professional burnout, namely such personality parameters as self-actualization of personality. It is noted that the phenomenon of burnout is associated with low scores on the following scales: “Values”, “Need for knowledge”, “Creativity”, “Autonomy”, “Spontaneity”, “Understanding of self”, “Autosympathy”.

Civil servants from the executive bodies of the Mykolaiv region have various manifestations of “professional burnout” syndrome. That is why there is a strong need for further serious and planned social and psychological intervention to prevent it and improve their professional engagement. Burnout negatively affects person's subjective quality of life. Such spheres as professional engagement, social status, health, recreation and mental health suffer the most. Internal well-being (self-understanding, self-acceptance, self-worth and self-management) is also distorted.

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